

Social Conditioning Experiments

"Stanley Milgram and Solomon Asch"

When the social mass is under pressure, people bow to the power of the group. By influencing individuals, whose perception, opinions, attitudes and behaviors are altered, everyone is led to conformism.

This psychological lever can be read between the plots of a "COVID-19 and its pilots", through the activation of obedience, with the prescription of an explicit rule.

Obedience is a principle that man learns from childhood, a system of rewards and punishments, "**he who obeys does not feel responsible for the action he carries out, while, he who gives orders and is obeyed is considered trustworthy and competent.**", whatever the orders are.

The lectures received, the restrictions imposed, in a slow and varied way, bring us back to the experiments and studies carried out by Milgram and Asch starting from 1951/1974

- **Stanley Milgram** was born in New York in 1933, to a family of Jewish and European origin. He earned his doctorate in social psychology from Harvard. He was a researcher and professor; his **experiment on obedience**, born to answer questions raised also by the tragedy of the Shoah and the Eichmann trial, it became well known and was at the center of its text *Obedience to authority* (1974).

- **Solomon Asch** was born in Warsaw in 1907. Moving to the United States, he earned his doctorate in psychology from Columbia University in 1932. His academic career led him to teach at various US universities and to head the social psychology section at the American Psychological Association. He died in Pennsylvania, in Haverford in 1996. His best known text is *Social psychology* (1952).

In an article published around the year 1999, it was highlighted that the mind deceives, through logical tests, demonstrating the deception, repeatable and verifiable events, through which, one arrives at the demonstration of scientific proof, to obtain answers certain, mathematically unassailable, since deceptions occur continuously in modern times.

Unfortunately it is pure and holy truth. Many things pass before our eyes without us realizing it, convinced that we are in the right without in the slightest realizing that suffering is being created for others. The experiment carried out by **Solomon Asch** the testimony is proof of this.

All this leads us to a new hypothesis, that is to a second apocalyptic theory, the prophecy of the Maya (the end of the world), given that the one of 21 December 2012 proved to be inaccurate, fortunately it is necessary to point out that many have missed the made of the permutability of digits, in the language of numbers. DI facts regarding the month the permutability cannot exist, since the inverse of 12 is 21, the month that corresponds to 21 does not exist, so the month is certainly DECEMBER. The day can be variable so we can have both 12 and 21, but that doesn't change a lot of things. Considering that the year 2012 has already passed, the next permutation, next is 2021, which together with the day, leads us to the apocalypse datable between 12/12/2021 and 21/12/2021. With numbers I have never been wrong in applying the theory of codes,

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